

NEWSLETTER

EMAI4EU

In-Sight

Edition 1 | May 2026

EMAI
4EU

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WELCOME!

We are excited to launch this new space where we will share the **latest news, achievements, events, and opportunities from the EMAI4EU community**. In each edition, we will take you behind the scenes of our work, highlight key milestones, and keep you informed about upcoming activities, learning opportunities, and developments in emotion AI, affective computing, and human-centric technology within Europe.

WOULD YOU STILL LOVE ME IF I WAS A MACHINE?

Challenge: Artificial Intelligence is increasingly pervasive in everyday life, but systems that can interpret human emotions and reactions remain a cutting-edge frontier of AI research.

EMAI4EU's response: training the next generation of Emotion AI specialists through a new European educational ecosystem.

The aim: strengthening Europe's advanced digital skills capacity and contributing to the growth of Artificial Intelligence, particularly Emotion AI (Affective Computing) across sectors and industries.

- ➔ Double-degree master's programme in Artificial Intelligence (ISCED Level 7, 120 ECTS), with a specialisation in Emotion AI and a minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship (I&E)
- ➔ Self-standing modules in Emotion AI, delivered both online and in person, leading to double certification pathways
- ➔ Education offers connecting higher education institutions, research centres, and innovative businesses across Europe
- ➔ Specialised training supporting upskilling and reskilling, particularly for professionals and a wider learner audience

OUR CONSORTIUM

Alone we can do so little, together we can do so much. — Helen Keller

EMAI4EU is coordinated by **28DIGITAL** and brings together **8 higher education institutions** and **5 innovative industry players** (SMEs and research-driven organisations). These partners offer a full range of complementary expertise to build a strong, sustainable European learning ecosystem for Artificial Intelligence. Find out more about us [HERE](#).

Developing a double-degree Master's programme and modular self-standing learning pathways in **Affective Computing**.

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CONSORTIUM LEADER

**28
DGTL**

ACADEMIC & RESEARCH PARTNERS

INDUSTRY & ECOSYSTEM PARTNERS

HOW DOES THE PROGRAMME WORK

Two countries, two universities, one shared learning journey. Students begin at an **Entry university** in year one, continue at an **Exit university** in year two, and complete the experience with the EIT Digital Summer School in between.

In the first year, they build a strong foundation in **computer science, data analysis, and human-machine interaction**, while also gaining **business and innovation skills**. In the second year, they deepen their expertise in **affective computing** and apply their knowledge to real-world challenges through a design project that combines technology with **entrepreneurship**.

Year 1 Entry University

Eötvös Loránd University
HUNGARY

Politecnico di Milano
ITALY

Université Côte d'Azur
FRANCE

University of Trento
ITALY

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
SPAIN

University of Rennes
FRANCE

University of Turku
FINLAND

AI WITH AFFECTIVE COMPUTING

Year 2 Exit University

Eötvös Loránd University
HUNGARY

EURECOM
FRANCE

Université Côte d'Azur
FRANCE

University of Trento
ITALY

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
SPAIN

University of Turku
FINLAND

Students must choose a different country and university for entry AND exit years

NEW TRAINING MODULES IN AFFECTIVE COMPUTING

Want to build skills to design systems that understand and respond to human emotion? EMAI4EU is developing **26 self-standing learning modules** to meet the need for additional education from both professionals and university learners.

EMAI4EU Courses

Alphabetical All Instructors

20 Lessons
Advanced Affective Computing
Kinga Bettina

20 Lessons
Advanced Innovation & entrepreneurship
Alvaro Pina Stranger

10 Lessons
Affective Computing with Case Studies
Kinga Bettina

0 Lessons
ANALYSIS OF MULTIMODAL INPU...
Juan Dapcich

These modules can be categorised into three main areas: **Data Science and Machine Learning, Human-Centred Interaction, and AI Ethics and Innovation.** They are offered through a single digital platform that combines self-paced online learning with topics ranging from **Knowledge Graphs and Deep Network Development** to **Emotion Identification through Biological Signals** and the **Ethics of Trustworthy AI.**

Learners can follow them either as stand-alone courses or as part of a specific area, with free access to all courses. Participants who complete the modules will also receive a **certificate of completion.**

STUDENTS' STORIES: WHY CHOOSE EMAI4EU?

Every student has a unique reason for choosing EMAI4EU, but for many, it comes down to the perfect balance of technology and personal growth. For **Zsombor Ádám**, currently studying at **Eötvös Loránd University** before he heads to **Madrid**, the choice was driven by a belief that AI is the future.

For **Nika Sharifi Dariani**, who is spending her journey between the **University of Trento** and **Université Côte d'Azur**, the programme is about much more than just classroom learning; it is a chance to develop as a person. Beyond her technical studies, she has embraced the cultural experience by learning Italian and immersing herself in a brand-new educational environment.

Both Zsombor and Nika encourage future students to leap: whether it's for academic excellence, cross-border mobility, or life-changing personal experiences, it's a journey where going the extra step makes all the difference.

EVENT HIGHLIGHTS

Since its launch, EMAI4EU has strengthened its visibility through a range of **outreach and promotional activities**. The programme was presented at several education fairs and student-oriented events, including the EIT Digital Master School Kick-off in Bari, the EIT Digital Master School Graduation Ceremony, the FIEP International Postgraduate Studies Fair in Madrid (24 November), Le Salon de L'Etudiant in Nice (29 November), and the SophiA Summit (19–22 November).

Beyond these student-focused activities, EMAI4EU was also featured in wider ecosystem-oriented events, including the “Unfiltered: The Truth About Entrepreneurship” workshop at the **Bosch Budapest Innovation Campus (12 March)**.

SUMMER SCHOOL

Looking ahead, the focus shifts to the upcoming **28DIGITAL EMPATHY AI Summer School in Madrid**, hosted by the **Technical University of Madrid (13–24 July)**, where students will spend two weeks exploring emotional intelligence and scalable digital innovation.

DROP-IN SESSIONS

EMAI4EU was also featured during several **EIT Digital Master School drop-in sessions** held throughout the year, including Université Côte d'Azur (20 Nov), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (12 Feb), Politecnico di Torino (19 Feb), Politecnico di Milano (24 Feb), and TalTech – Tallinn University of Technology (26 Feb).

WEBINARS

The programme was further promoted through the March online **information session**, Discover AIAC – Your Pathway into Artificial Intelligence & Affective Computing.” The webinar brought together programme leads and industry experts to introduce the AIAC track and show how the field goes beyond algorithms to better understand human behaviour and interaction.

LIVE Q&A

DISCOVER AIAC

Your pathway into Artificial Intelligence with Affective Computing (AIAC)

Monday, 23 March 2026, 16:00 CET

Tapio Pahikkala
Full Professor at UTU

László Gulyás
Associate Professor at ELTE

Marco Roveri
Associate Professor at UNITN

Logos: DGTL, Digital, EM-AI 4EU, and the European Union flag.

PARTNERS' PUBLICATIONS

EMAI4EU also shares insights through an **ongoing article series** led by project partners. The series opens up key topics around **affective computing, emotion-aware technologies, and human-centred AI** to a wider audience. Rather than scientific publications, the articles are accessible, insight-driven pieces that reflect perspectives from partners working across education, research, and innovation.

EMAI4EU PUBLICATIONS

- GenAI Emails in University Communications
- Exploring the future of Emotion AI and Gamified Health Apps
- Emerging Applications of Emotional Artificial Intelligence
- The Impact of Emotional Artificial Intelligence: Risks of Manipulation and Dehumanization
- Emotional AI: Helpful Companion or Ethical Mystery Box
- When Helpfulness Becomes a Vulnerability
- Emotions Enabling the New User Experience

EMAI 4EU logo and European Union flag.

WHAT NEXT?

The EMAI journey is evolving!

✨ Ready to take the next step? Our **results** speak for themselves: 92% of our alumni are employed after graduation, with 83% securing their first role within just three months. From AI specialists and affective computing researchers to innovators and entrepreneurs, our students are shaping the future of Artificial Intelligence and Emotion AI in Europe. Don't wait, apply now and join the next generation building Europe's AI future.

**APPLICATIONS FOR THE
THIRD ROUND CLOSE**

JUNE 1ST

Study across Europe and gain cutting-edge knowledge in Emotion AI, Human-Centered Computing, and Machine Learning.

If you're studying:

- Computer Science
- Cognitive Science
- Electrical Engineering
- Information Systems
- Mathematics

Then this Master's is made for you!

APPLY NOW!

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Subscribe to our newsletter and stay part of the **EMA I4EU community** for the latest news, events, and opportunities in artificial intelligence, affective computing, and human-centred innovation.

STAY TUNED FOR MORE UPDATES
FROM THE EMAI4EU COMMUNITY!

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Thank you